

VIRTUAL ANALYSIS OF INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEMS

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Abstract: These days, our everyday technological lifetime cannot be imagined without usage of the Internet. Today's the most significant and unstoppable process is that all the things, counting private data, banking activities, any services and information resources, are becoming connected to the Net, subsequent the data sources with recording and monitoring activities the working field because aimed of the privacy policy. With the high usage of Internet in today's life, security of network has become the key substance to all web applications, like online auctions, online retail sales, etc. This paper analyzes the factors which affect the library network security, such as data monitoring for e library management - An Intrusion Detection System (IDS), data security and so on, and puts forward corresponding security strategies and solutions. For safety purpose, the goal of the security system should be to provide a safe and secure facility for library employees, library resources and equipment and library patrons. At the same time due to application of security system, that promise to increase efficiency, productivity and enhance user satisfaction. As IDS is specialized for monitoring and recordings of network activities, the system has a big capability of prevention future intrusion, Intrusion Detection and Prevention Systems (IDPS) have become an important addition to the security infrastructure of nearly every organization.

Keywords: Internet use, Network, Information security, Digital libraries, Data protection, Intrusion Detection System (IDS).

An Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is a software application or device with main purpose of monitoring the system or activities of network for policy violations or malicious activities and generates reports to the management system. A number of systems may try to prevent an intrusion attempt but this is neither required nor expected of a monitoring system. The main focus of Intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDPS) is to identify the possible incidents, logging information about them and in report attempts. In addition,

organizations use IDPS for other purposes, like identifying problems with security policies, deterring individuals and documenting existing threats from infringing security policies. IDPS have become an essential addition to the security infrastructure of nearly every organization. Various methods can be used to detect intrusions but each one is specific to a specific method. The main goal of an intrusion detection system is to detect the attacks efficiently. Furthermore, it is equally important to detect attacks at a beginning stage in order to reduce their impacts.

Information coming from various response teams, during the last year, a computer was attacked or broken into more than once per second. These statistics may be only the tip of the iceberg as companies develop the ability to identify and track break-ins. The means for identifying and tracking break-ins is called “intrusion detection.” Intrusion detection systems (IDS), which have long been a topic for theoretical research and development, are gaining mainstream popularity as companies move more of their critical business interactions to the Internet. An intrusion detection system can provide advance knowledge of attacks or intrusion attempts by detecting an intruder’s actions.

In this respect, intrusion detection systems are a powerful tool in the organization’s fight to keep its computing resources secure. This guide will describe the primary sorts of intrusion detection technology and provide some guidance on how to select the right tools. Even though some may consider IDS tools just another check box in the audit compliance guideline, they should be planned as an integral part of the organizational network. As computer networks become ever more complex, intrusion detection will take on a greater role in the organization. An intrusion detection system attempts to uncover behavior or configurations that are, indicate, or could lead to malicious activity. Unfortunately, such a broad definition would lead you to believe that nearly anything, including papers describing system hardening, constitute intrusion detection systems. We must further constrain the definition. An intrusion detection system (IDS) is composed of hardware and software elements that work together to find unexpected events that may indicate an attack will happen, is happening, or has happened. Note that we must think in all three tenses; some products warn in advance that an attack may take place, some warn as they notice an attack in progress, and some warn when they notice the aftereffects of the attack.

Strengths

It is computationally infeasible to defeat the mathematics in an integrity checker. This makes it a very, very strong tool for detecting changes to files on a computer. It is so strong, in fact, that it is one of the most important tools you can use to detect misuse of computer systems. Honesty checkers can be configured to watch everything on the system, or only important files. They are extremely flexible. Once attackers compromise a system, they like to do two things. First, they like to cover up their tracks, which means that they will alter system binaries, libraries, or log files to hide the fact that they are or have been on the system. Second, they will make changes to ensure they will have continued access to the system. A properly configured file integrity checker will detect both activities.

Weaknesses

Integrity checkers rely on data stored on the local computers. Like log files, this data (the database of hash values) is vulnerable to modification on the system. Say an attacker gains superuser privileges on your system. The attacker can find the integrity checker, make any hostile changes to the system, and re-run the integrity checker to recreate the database of hash values. When the system administrator runs the tool, it will not report any changes to the system.

Finally, integrity checkers consume a considerable number of system resources." They can chew CPU, memory, and disk space. Many administrators will not want to run integrity checkers frequently. This limits their functionality, because a checker run once a month will report so many changes that a real attack has a good chance of going ignored.

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